

Students' participation in the internal quality assurance system and their role in enhancing learning

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Abstract

Quality assurance has seen many improvements since the Bologna Process in 1999 and internal quality assurance (IQA) systems have been emerging in Higher Education Institutions (HEIs), looking forward to the transparency and accreditation of study programs across Europe. Furthermore, quality systems should be focused on the improvement of students' experiences and, therefore, their learning. In this context, the effective involvement of students in the internal quality assurance system is vital to assure the enhancement process of teaching and learning and, consequently, the overall educational process.

Despite the variety of ways to obtain students' feedback, the most commonly used method by IQA systems is the pedagogical questionnaires. These have become an increasingly established way for students to have their voices taken into account. In this way, students can share their point of view, which is fundamental, because they have a clear and transparent perception of what is going well, as well as what is lacking in their study cycles, providing useful information for the IQA system. For this reason, these questionnaires are extremely important, and only with students' contribution, HEIs can act towards to improve.

Given the new developments of quality assurance, the purpose of the present paper is to emphasize the importance of students' involvement in the internal quality assurance system and propose methods to achieve it. Firstly, to understand the students' opinions regarding the pedagogical questionnaires, simple questions were applied to students of the University of Minho. The results showed that almost half of the students are unaware of the importance of their role in enhancing the quality of their HEI. To overcome this problem, HEIs might need to adjust their methodologies and processes to increase students' involvement in quality assurance. To this end, new strategies to capture students' attention and to improve the quality assessment are proposed.

Keywords: Higher education institutions; Internal quality assurance; Pedagogical questionnaires; Student engagement; Quality management.

1 Introduction

The concept of quality in Higher Education (HE) has become an increasingly important matter for institutions. Over the past fifty years, European HE has been undergoing reforms, however, since the late 1990s, the pace of change has significantly accelerated, mainly driven by the Bologna Process in 1999 (Diogo, 2014; Prisacariu, 2015). This is an intergovernmental HE reform process that emerged, mainly, to enhance the quality and recognition of European HE systems globally, encouraging a coherent and continuous development of quality (Reis, Formosinho and Lobo, 1974; Veiga and Amaral, 2009; Huet *et al.*, 2011; Diogo, 2014; Campanini and Bicocca, 2015; Fedeli, 2016).

Given this changing context, it is extremely important to implement a successful quality assurance system to guarantee and enhance the quality of Higher Education Institutions (HEIs). This can be reached through Internal Quality Assurance (IQA) and External Quality Assurance (EQA) (Figure 1). The first one occurs when the HEI carries out its own assessment using internal staff (e.g students) to check if policies and procedures set to ensure quality, meet the standards. The second one occurs when entities (governmental, para-state, or private agencies) carry out the assessment of the HEI (Keçetep and Özkan, 2014; Fedeli, 2016; Matei and Iwinska, 2016; Overberg *et al.*, 2019). In Portugal, the institution in charge of accrediting HEIs and courses is the *Agência de Avaliação e Acreditação do Ensino Superior* (A3ES). This is an autonomous institution, that aims to guarantee the quality of HEIs in Portugal, through evaluation and accreditation of its study cycles (Santos, 2011).

Figure 1. Quality assurance practices in HEIs.

Students are important stakeholders in the quality monitoring and assessment processes, and their participation in both external and internal quality assurance is vital (Alaniska *et al.*, 2006; Harvey, 2010). Currently, their involvement is mainly at the level of definition and political coordination of the evaluation process, in the pedagogical questionnaires, and in the participation in the audits managed by the external commission of evaluation (art. 12^o and 19^o Law 38/2007) (Lidice and Saglam, 2013).

Focusing on internal quality processes, HEIs implemented its own IQA system, which consists, mainly, of questionnaires that have to be filled in by students. These can be used for a quick gathering of information that helps the maintenance and improvement of the HEI quality (Friend-Pereira, Lutz and Heerens, 2002). Nevertheless, there is an ever-present difficulty that HEIs frequently deal with, caused by the lack of answers of students to this type of questionnaire. This led to the development of different studies on this matter (Little *et al.*, 2009; Lizzio and Wilson, 2009; Coffey and Gibbs, 2010; Little and Williams, 2010; Ryan, 2015). For instance, Elassy (Elassy, 2013) presented an interesting study where a model to increase students' involvement in QA was addressed, with great points to overcome this problem. Another interesting study was undertaken by Overbeg and her team (Overberg *et al.*, 2019), where a new procedure for internal quality management focusing on students' competences was considered and the questionnaires played an important role. Other authors only have shown that the role played by students is inevitably important. For instance, Lidice and Saglam (Lidice and Saglam, 2013) studied the students' perspective by asking them to comment and evaluate the educational quality, course objectives, the performance of their instructor, their learning, learning support they received, among other important factors. Their findings provided some useful insights and revealed certain action points for the development of the teaching program.

As can be seen, the students' participation in the IQA system is crucial. Their insight is a powerful tool in maintaining quality and enhancing learning, due to their engagement in the study cycles' processes. For this reason, they hold a perspective on teaching and learning that cannot be drawn from any other source (Ryan, 2015). Despite the different studies about the desirability of increasing student involvement in the QA systems, very few existing studies have focused on the particular issue of student involvement in the IQA system by showing new strategies to overcome the devaluation and position of indifference that students face the IQA system. In this regard, an important focus of this work lies on giving an overview of students' perspectives about the pedagogical questionnaires and explaining the necessity of developing new methodologies to capture their attention and involvement in evaluating and enhancing the quality of their HEI. Additionally, another strategy to guarantee quality maintenance is presented.

2 Students' role in the IQA system and improvement proposals

Students' involvement in evaluating and enhancing the quality of their HEI is carried out through various specific activities. Nevertheless, one of the thoroughly developed and most widely used method by the IQA systems to obtain students' feedback, is the pedagogical questionnaires (Ryan, 2015). These are extremely important to evaluate the teaching quality and educational performance of teachers, providing direct student input into decision-making and discussions about the study cycles and institutional development. In this way, students can openly share their opinion and suggest what should be improved, since only they know how they have reached their learning outcomes and how the teaching has assisted them in this process. (Little and Williams, 2010).

Students have the ability to evaluate the situation from the learner's perspective, which others may not be able to take into account and, since they have a special interest in the quality of the academic program, their statement is crucial (Alaniska et al., 2006). Also, involving students in IQA initiatives is beneficial because of their transparency, i.e. all participants see the outcomes and subsequent changes and, therefore, provide an important contribution for quality assurance in HEIs (Lidice and Saglam, 2013; Ryan, 2015; Akareem and Hossain, 2016).

Nevertheless, most students tend to ignore these questionnaires, making it difficult to correctly and completely evaluate a curricular unit (CU). To overcome this problem, the IQA system of the University of Minho (UM) opted to impose consequences on students who do not answer the questionnaires, making this process mandatory. To understand the students' opinion regarding the pedagogical questionnaires and if this mandatory process is actually needed, the following questions were made:

1. If it was not mandatory to answer the pedagogical questionnaires, would you still answer?
2. If you think that your study cycle needs improvements, do you write in the suggestions of the pedagogical questionnaires or ignore them? Justify your answer.

It is important to note here that this study was applied to all students of UM and only 25 answered. The results obtained for each question are represented in Figure 2 and Table 1, respectively.

Figure 2. Percent of answers to question 1.

Looking at Figure 1, it can be observed that 48 % of students would not answer the questionnaires if it did not involve consequences. The results show that, in fact, the measure implemented by the IQA system of UM seems to be necessary. Otherwise, almost half of the students would not answer the questionnaires.

Table 1. Examples of answers obtained in the second question.

	Positive answers	Negative answers
Statements	"Yes, it is one of the few ways that we have to express ourselves in a simple way"	"I think that our opinion is not taken seriously. If so, there would be serious improvements between years and complaints from past years would not be repeated. I think that if they took full advantage of our opinions as students, it would be essential."
	"Yes, this way the University will know about the failures of the course which will enable their improvement."	"I ignore because the measures suggested by students to improve the quality of teaching are not put into practice by the university or department."
	"Yes, since it is a way to better evaluate our CUs and consequently the teachers"	"I usually ignore because I think who analyzes the results are not interested in what the students really think or say. Because many times, people complain but no change is visible."
	"Yes, because there are always aspects to improve in the CUs"	"I ignore it for a matter of time. Sometimes I am not willing to waste time on questionnaires."
	"Yes. Because it is an opportunity for students to show their perspective of their CUs"	"I ignore because I don't think anyone will read that"
	"Yes, but only when something bothered me a lot."	"No, because if I have a complaint, I stop going to those classes."
	"Yes, when I vividly remember points to improve."	"No, because they do not change anything."

Despite the few data obtained, an overview of students' perspectives of quality in HE was obtained, and by observing Table 1, it can be concluded that the second question was ignored by most students, and only fourteen statements were obtained. This shows clearly that HEIs must act and promote students' participation. The biggest problem lies in students' lack of knowledge about the importance of their contribution to improving the quality of their HEI. One of the main reasons for this problem may be that the HEI does not adequately convey what it is doing to meet students' needs. In fact, UM shares the quality report of each study cycle with their students, however the measures they are willing to take to improve it, are missing, but more importantly, students are unaware of the existence of such documents. It should be highlighted that, to surpass this problem, the University of Minho has made some improvements, for instance, the website now presents all the necessary information on quality assurance processes. They even created a flyer that contains all the instruments and mechanisms used. Even so, students are still not aware of the importance of quality assurance in HEIs. To overcome this problem, it is necessary to communicate to students the importance of their answers to the quality assurance system and that their contribution is, effectively, considered.

Note that, although students are a remarkable part of the IQA, professors play a fundamental role as well, and, accordingly, at the University of Minho they have also to answer specific questionnaires developed for them. Moreover, course commissions are also important, because make a direct connection between the perspective of students and professors.

3 Strategies to capture students’ attention for its role in enhancing learning and to improve the quality maintenance

Given the important role of students in quality assurance, the development of strategic plans is crucial in the student-centered education context. In this sense, aiming to capture students’ attention for its role in enhancing learning, new strategies are suggested. This can be achieved in many different ways and in a simple manner. For instance by sending an institutional email to students stressing the importance of their contribution, instead of merely informing the deadline to answer. Another powerful tool is the role of professors’ testimony. They should work on persuading students about the importance of their views. Similarly, the delegate of each year must also take an active role in this matter, having the possibility to encourage students to answer the surveys and emphasize their role on IQA. The delegate can also transmit to the remaining colleagues the value of their participation, for instance, by means of social media, which nowadays, is the most powerful tool.

Additionally, another strategy that can attract students' attention is proposed, which is depicted in Figure 3. The idea would be to hold a meeting at the end of each year, in which the Course Director exposes to students the results from questionnaires and the measures they are considering implementing in the following year. Moreover, sharing measurements previously implemented by the study cycle would be of importance. This way, students would have the opportunity to actively contribute to improve their study cycle and see that, effectively, their opinions are taken seriously by the HEI and that is effective in the decision-making process.

Figure 3. Schematic methodology to encourage students’ participation in the IQA system.

Although the previous strategies are important, it is fundamental to use the information contained in the pedagogical questionnaires wisely. In Portugal, when the HE institution performs its auto-evaluation reports, the SWOT analysis is one of the tools applied. However, an extra methodology could be applied by having in consideration the Juran trilogy (Figure 4) applied in this context, i.e taking the students as costumers.

Figure 4. Juran Trilogy. Adapted from (McGrath and Bates, 2017).

According to Juran, quality is “fitness of use” and the emphasis should be on the customer. In this sense, the purpose of quality systems in higher education should act taking into account the enhancement of student experiences, by taking them as costumers (Santos, 2011). In this regard, after the SWOT analysis is completed, it is important to plan, control, and improve quality.

Firstly, the HEI should identify the student’s needs, based on the questionnaires and, then use that information to create processes that can fully satisfy the students’ needs. It should be developed and put in place the strategic and tactical goals that must be achieved. Note that this has already to be present in the auto-evaluation reports.

Secondly, during the implementation of reforms, the HEI should prevent or correct unwanted or unexpected changes, through periodic checks, measuring quality performance against expectations, identifying where the gaps are. This can be obtained by applying the same questionnaire in the middle of each semester and analyze the results.

Thirdly, quality planning could fail to meet student requirements and it is necessary to act in order to rectify any deficiencies and, therefore, improve the quality (McGrath and Bates, 2017). Establishing these steps, it is easier for the HEIs to improve the weaknesses and plan how to overcome the threats presented. It should be noted that this requires hard work from the HEIs since it is necessary to control the quality over the year, and it is not a task easy to take. However, it seems to be a powerful way to ensure that the HEI is effectively improving their quality by attending to students’ needs.

4 Conclusions

Quality Assurance is one of the key elements of the Bologna Process and IQA systems have been emerging in HEIs aiming to achieve the transparency and accreditation of study programs across higher education systems. In this context, the effective involvement of students in IQA is crucial to assure the improvement process of teaching and learning within the study cycles. Their view offers very useful information resource for IQA and has a great impact in shaping vision and encouraging HEIs to adapt and improve their services. Nevertheless, the results presented in this study showed that almost half of the students are unaware of the importance of their contribution through the pedagogical questionnaires and, therefore, in the IQA system. This is worrisome since students’ evaluation is a vital assessment instrument used for stimulating the quality enhancement of HEIs and without their active participation, this is difficult to achieve. This can be due to the feedback that HEI gives on the matter lacks details on what improvements they are prone to do and to what extent students’ opinion is considered. By applying the strategies proposed, changes are expected in students’ perception of quality and also in the quality evaluation process. Mainly, the strategy that involves holding a meeting at the end of each year with the students and the course director, is promising, because they can share their opinions and suggestions, and discuss the actions that should be implemented in the following year to enhance the quality of its study cycle. Despite the proposals presented in this study are based on the analysis of results obtained only at the University of Minho, they can be applied, if needed, at a national and international level

in order to enhance the quality management of HEIs. As previously mentioned, this will imply further work for all those involved in IQA, namely professors and course directors. Nevertheless, other perspectives should also be taken into consideration to improve the quality assessment process involved in HEIs. Thus, it is necessary to make use of multi-faceted approaches to the evaluation of HEIs' quality.

Acknowledgements

This work has been supported by FCT – Fundação para a Ciência e Tecnologia within the R&D Units Project Scope: UIDB/00319/2020.

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